

Merging, Recoiling, or Slingshotting of Supermassive Black Holes in a Red Active Galactic Nucleus

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Simulations and observational studies suggest that massive spheroidal galaxies grow by hierarchical merging. Such galaxies harbor supermassive black holes (SMBHs) in their centers, and the fate of the SMBHs during major mergers remains an intriguing question. The expectation is that the SMBHs lose their angular momenta via interactions with stars and the interstellar medium and quickly come into close proximity of each other (e.g., [1]). Eventually, the SMBHs will coalesce and emit a burst of low-frequency gravitational waves (GWs). The identification of SMBHs on the verge of merging could help constrain models of the evolution of SMBH-galaxy scaling relations (e.g., [2]). Moreover, future GW missions aim to detect GW signals from SMBH mergers; identifying the fraction of binary SMBHs with close separations can help in predicting the detection rate for such missions.

However, observational studies have difficulty finding such multiple SMBH systems. There are examples of active galactic nuclei (AGNs)—bright compact objects that are powered by accretion of matter by SMBHs in the centers of galaxies—with separations of about a kiloparsec or less, but only a

Figure 1. (a) The complex H α line profile of 1659+1834. The black line shows the observed GMOS spectrum, and the purple line indicates the best fitting multi-component model. Blue and red curves trace the primary and secondary broad components, respectively; the cyan curve shows the narrow line component. (b) Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS; [10]) r-band image of the host galaxy, showing extended features interpreted as tidal tails resulting from a galaxy merger. (c) HST/WFPC2 F814W image showing the central structure of 1659+1834. (d) Derived spatial distributions of the flux from the two broad H α components; the spatial offset between the centers is significant. (Adapted from [8], with permission)

handful of such systems have been discovered (e.g., NGC 6240 [3]). Models predict that gas-rich galaxy mergers evolve through a highly obscured phase during which the AGN appears very red until the final SMBH merger occurs [4]. Thus, the best place to look for SMBHs in the process of merging may be within the red AGNs of morphologically irregular galaxies.

We have been studying red AGNs to test the merger-driven SMBH evolution scenario, finding supporting evidence such as red colors originating from dust extinction [5], [6] and high accretion rates associated with red AGNs [6], [7]. Among the sources we have studied [8] is the intriguing red AGN 2MASS J165939.7+183436 (hereafter 1659+1834) at $z = 0.170$. This object has double-peaked broad emission lines (BELs) separated by $\sim 3000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and the host galaxy shows clear signs of merging (Figure 1b,c). If there is also a spatial separation between the two BEL components, then this would indicate separate BEL regions around two different SMBHs. Using the measured luminosities and line widths of the two H α BELs and the relation from [9], we estimate primary and secondary black hole masses of $10^{8.9 \pm 0.1}$ and $10^{7.1 \pm 0.1} M_{\odot}$.

Figure 2. Models for the doubled-peaked AGN 1659+1834. (a) A stable binary SMBH system would produce lower velocities (or a much smaller separation) than observed. (b) A hot accretion disk around a central SMBH can produce double-peaked broad emission, but the size would be much smaller than the estimated spatial offset. (c) A recoiling SMBH, in which a merger of two SMBHs releases energy in GWs and causes the newly merged SMBH to recoil. (d) Gravitational slingshot: a binary SMBH gravitationally ejects the smaller intruder SMBH3 at a speed of thousands of km s^{-1} . Models (c) and (d) are consistent with the data. (From [8], with permission)

We observed 1659+1834 at Gemini North using the GMOS Integral Field Unit (IFU) and modeled the spatially resolved spectra with two broad components and one narrow-line component (Figure 1a). The narrow component was found to be spatially coincident with the dominant (or primary) broad component. However, the centroid of the flux associated with the secondary BEL component was offset by $0.085''$ (Figure 1d), corresponding to a physical separation of 250 pc, with an estimated uncertainty range from $0.04''$ to $0.15''$. A variety of models were considered to explain the observed spatial and velocity offsets; the models are illustrated schematically in Figure 2.

Our analysis [8] found that a binary SMBH system in a stable orbit could not explain the observations, as the measured velocity offset of 3000 km s^{-1} is 10 times higher than would be expected even if the SMBHs were near the pericenter of an elliptical orbit. Likewise, double-peaked emission from a rapidly rotating disk around a single SMBH would produce a much smaller spatial separation. However, the third explanation—a recoiling SMBH—could reproduce the observed velocity and spatial offsets as long as the BEL region remains gravitationally bound to the recoiling SMBH. Finally, a 3-component gravitational slingshot

scenario, involving a “small” SMBH system that approaches a binary SMBH and is ejected at high speed along with its BEL region, can also account for the observations.

Interestingly, both of the viable models for 1659+1834 involve three SMBHs. However, the interpretation depends critically on the size of the 250 pc spatial offset between the BEL components. We have pushed the limits of what can be done with the GMOS-N IFU with excellent natural seeing and by performing a careful analysis of the two observed BEL components. Further studies using adaptive optics, very-long baseline interferometry, and/or the *James Webb Space Telescope* are needed to confirm these results on this unusual system.

References

- [1] Escala, A., et al. 2005, *ApJ*, 630, 152
- [2] Kormendy, J. & Ho, L. C. 2013, *ARA&A*, 51, 511
- [3] Komossa, S., et al. 2003, *ApJL*, 582, L15
- [4] Blecha, L., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 478, 3056
- [5] Kim, D. & Im, M. 2018, *A&A*, 610, A31
- [6] Kim, D., et al. 2018, *ApJS*, 238, 37
- [7] Kim, D., et al. 2015, *ApJ*, 812, 66
- [8] Kim, D., et al. 2020, *ApJ*, 894, 126
- [9] Greene, J. E. & Ho, L. C. 2007, *ApJ*, 670, 92
- [10] Dey, A., et al. 2019, *AJ*, 157, 168